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A mild and efficient H₂O₂ oxygenation of N-heteroaromatic compounds to the amine N-oxides and KI deoxygenation back to the tertiary amine with hexaphenyloxodiphosphonium triflate

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Abstract

A mild and efficient method for the oxidation of N-heteroaromatic compounds to the corresponding N-oxides using H₂O₂ in the presence of hexaphenyloxodiphosphonium triflate (Hendrickson reagent) in EtOH at room temperature was reported. This methodology presented relatively fast and selective reactions to afford the N-oxides in good yields. The reverse reactions, deoxygenation reactions, were also carried out under the same reaction conditions by KI to produce the tertiary amines.

Keywords: Oxidation, N-Heteroaromatic compound, N-Oxide, Hydrogen peroxide, Hexaphenyloxodiphosphonium triflate.